

Creative Collaborations:

Inspiring Engagement by Hosting an NLM Traveling Exhibit

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Purpose

- Showcase how our library engaged users through programming and partnerships
- Highlight creative events surrounding the NLM traveling exhibit
- Share lessons learned and outcomes

About the Exhibit

Exhibit Title

Take 2 and Call Me in the Morning: the Story of Aspirin Revisited

Provided by

National Library of Medicine

Theme Focus

History and impact of aspirin

Take 2
& Call Me
in the Morning

The Story of Aspirin Revisited

Traveling Exhibit!
Medical Center Library | April 28 to June 7

Opening Reception & Rare Book Pop-Up
May 5, 11:30am to 1:30pm

Free Drug Resources Workshop
April 30, 12:00pm to 1:00pm

Above: Chemists in Leeds University Laboratories, 1908
Courtesy National Library of Medicine

Below: "The Willow," A Curious Herbal: containing five hundred cuts... Volume 2, Elizabeth Blackwell, c. 1739
Courtesy National Library of Medicine

The National Library of Medicine produced this exhibition.
GUEST CURATOR: Anne Rothfeld, PhD
DESIGNER: HealyKohler Design

NIH National Library of Medicine

MedlinePlus
Trusted Health Information for You

Planning Process: Timeline

Jan/Feb
2025

Field trips to
collaborating
libraries

April 30, 2025
Free Resource
Workshop

May 5, 2025
Rare Book
Pop Up Exhibit

Aug 2024
Brainstormin
g & Planning
Group
formed

April 28, 2025
First day
of Exhibit

May 5, 2025
Opening
Reception

June 7, 2025
Last day
of Exhibit

Collaborative Partnerships

Libraries Involved:

- Four campus libraries

Purpose:

- Highlight diverse resources across the system

Impact:

- Strengthened interdepartmental relationships

Opening Reception

- **Features:**

- Book displays from collections
- Refreshments and promotional items

- **Special Event:**

- Pop-up exhibit by Rare Books Librarian
- Herbal Medicine texts from donor collection

The Willow.
E. W. Blackwell delin. sculp. et Pinx. } *Salix.*
1. Catkin.
2. Seed & Pericarp.
3. Seed & Pericarp Separate.
4. Seed & Pericarp open.
5. Seed.

Event and Display

Rare Book Display featuring materials donated by Dr. Charles T. Ambrose

Educational Programming

Webinar:

- Hosted by the Pharmacy Liaison Librarian
- Topic: Open access drug information resources

Herbal Flower Display:

- Inspired by NLM's digital collections
- Visual and thematic enhancement

Webinar

FREE & CLEAR

An Introduction to Reliable
Open Access Drug Resources

Workshop recording "Free & Clear: An Introduction to
Reliable Open Access Drug Resources"

Herbal Flower Display

Display based on individual flowers and plants that were used in early herbal medicine, each tagged with a descriptive blurb from the 1737 text *A Curious Herbal* by Elizabeth Blackwell

Challenges & Adaptations

Unexpected changes:

- Adjustments to original plans

Lessons Learned:

- Flexibility in programming
- Importance of communication and contingency planning

Outcomes & Impact

User Engagement:

- Increased awareness of library services
- Highlighted unique collections

Systemwide Benefits:

- Strengthened visibility and collaboration

Final Thoughts

- Creativity enhances engagement
- Collaboration multiplies impact
- Exhibits can be springboards for broader programming

Questions?

All of the presenters can be reached via
email at mclib@uky.edu

La Cartame ou Safran bâtard.
Carthamus Tinctorius, Linn.
Ital. Cartamo. Angl. Bastard Saffron. Allem. Wilder Safran.